

**ENVIROSENSEHEALTHMONITOR : A DESIGN APPROACH TO BRIDGE GAP BETWEEN ENVIROTNEMENT
HEALTH AND PERSONAL WELL BEING**

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Human health is intimately linked to the state of the environment. Air pollution continues to rise at an alarming rate, wreaking havoc on human health. Currently for individuals to obtain life saving insights, they must travel to locations of specialized equipment like hospitals or buy expensive health equipment. There is a dire unmet social need for individuals to have an ability to easily, accurately and holistically measure, monitor and detect changes in health conditions in a given environment. "EnviroSenseHealthMonitor" is a one-stop solution that transforms healthcare by helping people understand and monitor their own health. This single comprehensive health monitoring device has the capability to measure key vital health biosignals such as lung, heart, brain and general well being. It also correlates the health insights with the changing environment such as (Air Pollution)AQI and weather. It provides alerts, recommendations and devised plans for preventive care, early intervention or recovery.

Present Technology:

Health gadgets and mobile apps are incredible tools to provide insights into many bodily functions and track gains and improvements. There are a variety of options available today in the market that measure specific bodily functions. There are monitors and applications available for air pollution, weather as well. Some example of devices/trackers available in market are:

1. Wearable devices such as fitness trackers and smartwatches can track activity levels, heart rate, sleep patterns, and other health metrics.
2. Smart scales and body composition monitors can track weight, body fat percentage, and other body composition metrics.
3. Blood pressure monitors and glucometers can track blood pressure and blood sugar levels.
4. Telemedicine platforms allow patients to consult with healthcare providers remotely.
5. Medication reminders can help patients stay on track with their medication regimen.
6. Remote monitoring devices can enable healthcare providers to monitor patients' vital signs and other health metrics remotely.
7. Smart Pill Bottles and Medication Dispensers can remind you to take medication.
8. Smart Thermometers can take temperature and store it for future reference.
9. AQI meters used indoors or outdoors can track air pollution levels.
10. Weather centers and applications for forecasting.

Health monitoring devices are designed to have a specific purpose, for example, an oximeter is used for measuring blood oxygen saturation level. Users need to buy a variety of such gadgets to meet their need of monitoring their overall well being. In addition, pre-existing disease patients would also need to make regular hospital/lab visits for specialized equipment

testing such as spirometry, diabetes testing. Respiratory diseases are perfect examples of chronic diseases currently managed in this way. Asthma is one of the most common of these diseases, affecting one in twelve people (approximately 25 million individuals in the United States alone), which in 2007, resulted in 56 billion dollars of medical expenses and thousands of preventable deaths .

All this health and environmental data is currently fragmented and unorganized. There is a problem that these plethora of gadgets do not communicate with each other. Hospital equipment data is in the form of written reports. Due to lack of organization of information at one place and the user's health is at risk especially in environments which are polluted. Also, these gadgets are quite expensive and often unaffordable for the majority of people. Today, Environmental data like Air Quality Index, Weather, temperature is available through public datasets, satellite data and users can view them on demand using various mobile applications. With rapid advancements in IoT, AI and Machine learning, if all this data could be organized, analyzed and interpreted at common place, it could become very useful in predicting onset of such chronic diseases like lung, heart, brain and could help quantify the magnitude of environmental changes impact on human health.

History:

Air pollution measurement has a long history, dating back to ancient civilizations. Some of the earliest milestones in the history of air pollution measurement comes from Ancient Greece, where philosopher Aristotle described the impact of air pollution on health and environment. In modern history, air pollution measurement happened in the 19th century. In 1852, Scottish chemist Robert Angus measured the acidity of the rain drops because of high

sulfur coming from coal burning. This led the UK to pass the “clean air act” in 1956, the very first legislation to prevent air pollution by any country. Later, the United States passed its clean air act in 1963 and by 1970 it was first linked to impact on human health.

Humans have been measuring biosignals or vital signs since the dawn of HumanIt was only in the early 20th century that Irish physician and environmental engineer, John Switzer Owens greatly advanced the methods of air pollution measurement by applying a network of deposit gauges at various locations. Then in December of 1952, great fog of London happened for 5 days and led to killing of more t civilization especially for body temperature and pulse rate. But, the first ever device to measure a vital sign came from Galileo who built a spirit thermometer to measure body temperature and used a pendulum to measure the pulse. Thereafter, respiratory rate was included as one of the factors and it was only in 1896, first spygomamometer (blood pressure cuff) was made to measure blood pressure. The real revolution for these devices came with the advancement in modern electronics in the 1960's and 1970's where these vital signals could be measured more accurately, stored and printed. This led to rapid advancement in the field of medicine. While these devices continued to get better and better in hospital/clinic settings, the real paradigm shift happened with the use of portable medical devices that patients could measure vital signs anywhere. So, now a patient could be monitored in other settings leading to development of preventive care routines and protocols. With advancements in networking, wireless lan and bluetooth, these portable devices became connected portable devices and could now send the measurements to remote locations. As a next logical step, it is just matter of time that this data will be organized, collated and analyzed at a more minute level to deliver more sophisticated medical care to people.

Future Technology:

“EnviroSenseHealthMonitor” is a one-stop, cost effective solution which includes a device and mobile application for people to get healthier in their own living environment. The device has sensors and state of art technology to conduct a series of tests which are critical to assess comprehensive health and overall wellbeing of an individual. It has the capability to measure and monitor lung, heart, brain health, all in one!

The system comprises of following components:

Component/Sensor	Purpose/Measures	Technology
LED, Photodetector for PPG(photoplethysmography), Camera	Heart Rate, Breathing Rate, BP, Oxygen Saturation, Heart rate variability, Diabetes	Finger Photoplethysmography (PPG) is an optical technique that measures blood volume variations. The main application of dual-wavelength PPG is pulse oximetry, in which the arterial oxygen saturation (SpO ₂) is calculated noninvasively. By using videos of fingertips captured with camera, heart rate (HR), heart rate variability can be estimated using the photoplethysmography (PPG) technique. The extracted signal is fed into a convolutional regression neural network which outputs the estimated HR. The results obtained are compared with the ground truth HR obtained by using a contact PPG sensor. The same algorithm is expanded to measure the respiratory rate, BP, Diabetes continuously and instantly.
AQI Sensor	Air Quality monitoring	Air quality sensor to measure for Particulate matter, Black carbon and other hazardous gasses to monitor Indoor Air pollution
MEMS Thermal Film Flow sensor, Extension	Spirometry for chronic lung disease patients	Both inspiration and expiration breath-flows of the patient have to be

respiratory tract tube for patient		measured precisely to permit the identification of any deviation compared to a healthy person. To attain this aim a very sensitive MEMS based thermal flow sensor is integrated into a “EnviroSenseHealthMonitor”. User blows breath through replaceable extendable tract tube. To guarantee the reproducibility of the flow measurements a high accuracy algorithm is designed.
Infrared Sensor	Temperature	Infrared(IR) temperature sensors measure the infrared energy emitting from an object in order to determine the temperature of the object.
Soli sensor	Sleep Study through Non-contact (radar) sleep trackers	A low-energy radar transmitter which scans the body many times per second, allowing the device to detect tiny variations in your movement whilst you sleep, from which it can determine breathing and heart rate data. This makes our device as a nearable that you place in the bed or mattress. It monitors your body movement, heart rate and breathing. Uses machine learning technology to translate that data into sleep metrics you can view and analyze later.
microphone	Detects Cough, Snoring, Chest Wheezing sounds	
Bluetooth		To communicate with the phone over BLE
WiFi		To Communicate with cloud services, data sets, hospital, primary care, outdoor AQI sensor data sets, weather data
Hardware Board	Raspberry Pi - model 4	This hardware board will allow connection of all the sensors to the

		CPU running the software and display information to the user.
Smart Phone Application		EnviroSenseHealthMonitor app for assisting users to measure, monitor and detect changes in health conditions end to end in their own living environment. Also providing capability to provide preventive or pre-existing, or recovery care in association with primary care doctor and hospital.
Cloud Data		

As shown above in the table, there are several sensors in the device with corresponding embedded software, ML and AI, which provides the ability to accurately measure Heart Rate, Breathing Rate, BP, Oxygen Saturation, Heart rate variability, Diabetes, Spirometry, Temperature, Sleep study, listens to cough & snoring.

Regular testing using “EnviroSenseHealthMonitor” can help detect health conditions around the vital organs such as lung, brain, heart, diabetes. Spirometry is a critical test for measuring lung capacity for people suffering from lung diseases. In air polluted environments, the ability to perform this test with such ease will lead to a healthier and happy life for patients and their caregivers.

“EnviroSenseHealthMonitor” application needs to be installed on the user’s phone. The device sends all the test results, indoor AQI to the phone application via Bluetooth. Phone application also pulls Outdoor air pollution AQI data, weather forecast from public datasets over WiFi and performs data analysis to correlate with user’s health data to provide insights, guidance, recommendations and alerts. EnviroSenseHealthMonitor data is also stored in cloud (based on

user's consent) for providing access to researchers and policy makers to learn and make decisions around impact of air pollution and climate change on Human health.

Dataflow of EnviroSenseHealthMonitor

“EnviroSenseHealthMonitor” solves some of these customer Critical User Journeys or needs:

User needs and challenges in air polluted environment

User monitoring health (preventive)

Needs to catch symptoms early & reduce need of emergency/serious care

Challenge:

- 1) No single way to measure, monitor overall health to provide alerts/notification
- 2) Plethora of fitness gadgets and health monitoring devices required which are unaffordable to critical mass
- 4) No way to provide correlation of health insights with environmental changes such as air pollution, weather, wind, temperature.

User with pre-existing disease condition

Needs to visit regularly to hospital, nearby clinics to perform medical exams such as Spirometry, Breathing rate, Heart rate, Sleep study, Blood pressure, Haematology etc.

Challenge:

- 1) No mechanism available to perform at-home self tests which are auto-logged and shared with primary doctor
- 2) No prompts to perform self tests in case environmental conditions are non-conductive
- 3) No guidance on increasing/decreasing dosage based on environmental conditions and test results
- 4) No way to provide alerts/notifications to guide on prioritize scheduling hospital visits

User struggling with the disease (say asthma, copd)

Needs to frequently monitor health parameters such as lung capacity, hearth, breather rate, quality of sleep, snoring, cough, sneeze, wheezing, of chest and report results to primary hospital for real-time remote care.

Challenge:

- 1) Hospitalization is mandatory due to lack of high quality remote care and monitoring options

Breakthroughs:

It is important to measure various biosignals with utmost accuracy so that they can eventually be shared with medical professionals for better diagnosis. Today, some of the measurements have an error rate greater than 5~6 % which makes it less trustworthy for medical use. Another problem is some of these biosignals measurements need handling of the devices which is a barrier for everyday and every time measurement. So, breakthrough for this solution would be improved accuracy of non-invasive mechanisms to measure biosignals.

Blood work is an important marker of one's health. Everyday monitoring would need blood testing to happen with a single prick for a single drop of blood. Today, we don't have the technology to measure various parameters in blood with just a single drop of blood. Once available this breakthrough will revolutionize the healthcare industry.

Design Process:

One of the most important things for “EnviroSenseHealthMonitor” is the accurate measurement of biosignals. We considered various designs to measure these biosignals accurately. One such design involved the use of a thermal camera for accurately measuring Breathing Rate. Thermal camera can detect the temperature of breath going in and out of a person’s nostrils and count them to calculate breathing rate. This mechanism was dropped because thermal cameras of sufficient accuracy are expensive, like more than \$500. Also, we found another cost effective and accurate way to measure Breathing rate by using a high resolution camera focussed on a person’s chest and monitoring subtle movements of the chest going up and down. This method was found highly accurate with ~1% error rate.

Conclusion:

Availability of such a device will have a lot of positive consequences for managing human health. With inevitable deterioration of our air and climate change it is more than necessary that we are prepared to measure their impact on human health.

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